

Long-Term Barrier Performance Under Heating and Cooling Cycles: An Experimental Analysis of Grouting and Pellets Behaviour for HT-ATES Systems

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Keywords: Grout, Clay-pellets, wellbore integrity

ABSTRACT

Underground thermal energy storage has a key role in the energy transition. HT-ATES (high-temperature aquifer thermal energy storage) is a promising technology for seasonal thermal energy storage. To enhance the thermal performance and ensure the long-term integrity of HT-ATES wells, selecting an annular material for such well completions with low thermal conductivity and high sealing capacity is essential.

This research develops and uses a novel experimental framework and imaging processing to visualize and evaluate the sealing capacity of grouting materials and clay pellets over thermal heating and cooling cycles. The fully developed apparatus allows to measure the spatial variation of the temperature at different distances. An aluminum tube represents the wellbore completion tubing with the annular material cured in place for 7 and 28 days. During the heating and cooling cycles, the temperature alternates between 90°C, 40°C and 22°C; hence, the tubing and the annular material are subjected to a stress variation due to the expansion and contraction. The characteristics of the interface and microstructure are analysed using micro CT-scanning, with the 3D reconstruction demonstrating that low stiffness grouting materials exhibit debonding and deformation in the interface region for 7 days curing period.

A uniform deformation around the tubing describes the plastic behaviour of the materials. Sand particle migration from the sand layer to the interface clearly demonstrates the preferential fluid path during injectivity tests, corresponding to a compromise in the interface due to thermal cycles. Strong bonding and an intact interface are observed for grouting materials, with a significant increase in strength and stiffness after 28 days of curing compared to 7 days. On the other hand, samples with a lower increase demonstrated a slight deformation at the interface and thermal cracks at the edge of the sample.

In contrast, clay pellets showed high swelling capacity and plasticity, corresponding to continuous sealing of the annular space for freshwater experiments. For experiments conducted with 0.25 mol/L NaCl the results indicate a significant decrease in swelling capacity.

This work provides a robust and repeatable experimental framework and analysis to assess the long-term sealing capacity for HT-ATES systems considering various annular materials and representative conditions.

1. INTRODUCTION

High energy demand and the need to reduce the use of fossil fuels have accelerated the development of the renewable energy sector. During summer, thermal energy demand reaches its lowest point while availability of renewable heat is high in summer. Thus, underground thermal energy storage has a key role in the energy transition (Oosterholt et al., 2018; Bloemendal et al., 2021; Vardon et al., 2024). HT-ATES (high-temperature aquifer thermal energy storage) system is a promising technology for thermal energy storage. Efficient thermal energy extraction is a function of grouting, cement, or pellets, well design, flow rates and formation properties (Kutun et al., 2014; Brown & Falcone, 2024). Optimizing well performance has considerable challenges during the drilling and completion phases, particularly targeting heterogeneous and deep aquifers (Koulidis et al., 2025). For low temperature aquifer thermal energy storage (LT-ATES) systems, the completion and annular materials are subjected to low temperature variations (Pellegrini et al., 2019) compared to HT-ATES where the temperatures can reach 90°C. Large temperature variations during extraction, injection, and well rehabilitation results in thermally-induced stress.

To enhance the thermal performance of an HT-ATES system, selecting an annular material with low thermal conductivity and high sealing capacity is essential. During the completion of a conventional well (cylindrical borehole), the annular space between the

borehole and the casing is backfilled with grouting or pellets, which act as sealing materials to prevent wellbore collapse and water migration. To enhance the efficiency of the system, the grouting materials are selected depending on the applications. Grouting chemical composition primarily consists of bentonite and additional mixtures, including silica-sand and graphite (Lee et al., 2010; Lee et al., 2011). In the field, thermal response tests (TRT) are essential to evaluating the in-situ thermal properties of the grout-mixture by injecting constant heat flow in the wellbore (Austin III, 1998; Borinaga-Treviño et al., 2013).

Various studies have been conducted to investigate the effect of mechanical loading in the cement sheath due to temperature variation for deep wells (Goodwin & Crook, 1992; Ichim & Teodoriu, 2017). The results indicate debonding between the casing and the cement sheath, resulting in the formation of micro-annulus and thermal cracks (De Andrade et al., 2015; Han et al., 2023).

The objective of this work is to experimentally evaluate the effect of heating and cooling cycles on the sealing capacity of grout and pellet materials for high-temperature and low-stress conditions. This work replicates relevant temperature scenarios observed in a potential HT-ATES system, thus, high amplitude temperature cycles.

2. MATERIALS

2.1 Grouts

The current case study utilizes commercial grouts. The three products are known in the industry as suitable materials for conventional ATES systems and groundwater wells. The supplier partially provides the thermal and mechanical properties and chemical composition, and thus, these parameters are determined in additional experiments. The grout mixtures consisted of mixed components: graphite, bentonite, cementation minerals and silica sand. The X-ray diffraction (XRD) analysis shows the following compositions:

- Grout 1 has a considerably higher concentration of cementation minerals and concentrations of montmorillonite and quartz.
- Grout 2 has a considerably higher concentration of graphite and quartz.
- Grout 3 has a lower concentration of cementation minerals and quartz.
- Grout 4 has a higher concentration of montmorillonite and calcite and contains quartz and calcite.

Additionally, Grout 1 was evaluated using a specific concentration of silica sand with particle size distributions of 250-500 μm (Grout 1, S2) and 500-1000 μm (Grout 1, S1), respectively.

2.2 Clay-pellets

Clay pellet materials are specifically evaluated to isolate the drilled clay layers. The high swelling

capacity provides borehole sealing on clay zones and can be utilized with fresh and high-salinity water. The clay-pellets have the following composition:

- Clay-pellet 1 contains calcium montmorillonite clay and quartz.
- Clay-pellet 2 contains calcium montmorillonite clay and magnetite, which is utilized as a variable to detect the annular materials and intervals in the subsurface.

3. EXPERIMENTAL PROCEDURE

3.2. Mechanical properties

During the heating and cooling cycles, the grout is subjected to a significant variation of stress caused by the expansion and contraction of the tubing material and the grout itself. The uniaxial compression and tensile tests aim to determine the mechanical properties of the samples. The experiments are conducted for curing periods of 7 and 28 days, which complies with the actual field conditions and is followed by ASTM testing standards (ASTM-D7012-14, 2014; ASTM-D3967-23, 2023). The Brazilian test is an indirect measurement of the sample's tensile strength. Maximum load is recorded and the tensile strength for that particular sample can be calculated by knowing the dimensions of the sample, as shown in equation [1].

$$\sigma_t = \frac{2F}{\pi dl} \quad [1]$$

where σ_t is the tensile strength [MPa], F is the applied force [N], d is the sample diameter [mm], and l is the sample length [mm]. The stress-strain relationship shows that for the 7-day curing period, the samples have a short elastic limit and significantly deform after reaching the maximum stress, which corresponds to ductile material behaviour. This phenomenon can be observed for both tests. In particular, it is observed that (Figure 1) the sample behaves as an ideal plastic material

(a)

(b)

Figure 1: Stress-strain and load–displacement data for the grouting material for (a) UCS and (b) Brazilian test

During 28 days of curing, the peak stress and elastic limit significantly increased for Grouts 1 and 2, with Grout 4 showing limited changes. Concerning Grout 3, due to the low strength of the sample during 7 days of curing, the UCS and Brazilian tests cannot be performed. The W/G ratio is 6.20, indicating a liquid mixture with much higher water content than the other grout mixtures.

3.2. Thermal cycles apparatus

The setup allows consistent temperature variations to simulate the heating and cooling cycles during the lifespan of an HT-ATES system. The heating cycle corresponds to a temperature between 80°C to 90°C in the inner part of the aluminium tube, and the cooling cycle is from 40°C to laboratory temperature (22°C). The wellbore completion is recreated with an aluminium tube in the center and the heating element (heat source) mounted in place with a thermal paste. The apparatus contains four thermocouples to control the heating element's temperature and measure the temperature's spatial variation at different distances. Compared to the actual field case, the hot or cold water circulates in the casing and flows in both directions depending on the charging or discharging of the system. The water transfers heat in the axial direction with conduction heat exchange with the casing. The heat generated from the frictional component due to fluid contact with the casing is relatively small for shallow wells, and is neglected. Figure 2 demonstrates the heating and cooling cycles for Grout 4. The controller regulates the heating element temperature and is switched on with a target temperature of 90°C, controlled via the inner thermocouple (P1). P2 and P3 are thermocouples located 15 mm and 30 mm in the sample, respectively.

Figure 2: Thermal cycles during testing Grout 4 with measuring the temperature on different locations

3.3. Image processing

Micro-computed tomography (micro-CT) was utilized to characterize the samples. The distance between the base (sample location) and the X-ray source was adjustable and deviated for each sample. Thus, each sample's region of interest (ROI) was slightly different. The acquired files contained relative information about each scan, including resolution, scanning time and voxel size.

4. RESULTS

4.1. Grouts – 7 days of curing period

As it was presented in Figure 1, the grouts have a range of mechanical properties. As the aluminium tube is heated, the metal is expanded. The rate at which the size of the metal changes is a function of the thermal expansion coefficient. The tube expansion applies thermal stress to the annular material. The magnitude of the stress is a function of the thermal and mechanical properties of the tube and annular material, and the rate of temperature change. During the expansion and contraction of the tube, the annular space differs as it is presented in the graphical schematic Figure 3.

Figure 3: Graphical illustration of the effect of heating and cooling cycles on plastic materials

Figure 4, shows a micro-CT scan that demonstrates a slight deformation in the interface between the tube and

the Grout 4. It is also observed that the cycling of heating and cooling creates cracks at the edge of the sample. The slight deformation exceeds the tensile strength of the grouting material, creating radial cracks at the edge of the sample.

Figure 4: Image reconstruction of Grout 4

The entire experimental framework has been performed at a relatively constant laboratory temperature of 22°C with a variation of 1°C. Figure 5 presents the spatial distribution of the temperature across the different samples during the tests for locations 1.5 cm (P2) and 3.0 cm (P3) from the centre (Figure 5a and Figure 5b respectively).

(a)

(b)

Figure 5: Temperature profile during one cycle versus dimensionless time. The duration of the heating process is slightly differ for each grout due to the manual activation of the controller.

Even though Grout 2 has significantly higher thermal conductivity than Grout 1 and 4, the inner thermocouple shows a sharper temperature increase for Grout 4. The micro-CT scan images and camera-based photos are utilized to measure the exact location of the thermocouples from the edge of the casing, which indicates distances of 4.0 mm, 4.4 mm and 2.40 mm for Grouts 1, 2 and 4, respectively. The long, thin thermocouples show sensitivity during the installation and curing process. Figure 6 shows that sand particles were mobilised during water injection with a 100 ml/min flow rate. The thermal cycles result in the formation of an additional space in the interface, demonstrating a plastic deformation of the Grout 1.

Figure 6: Extracted material from Grout 1 that demonstrates sand mobilization

Figure 7 demonstrates the 3D reconstruction of the image stack, with yellow representing the additional annular space created by the thermal cycles. The results indicate a uniform plastic deformation in the top part of the tubing for Grout 2 and resilience in the thermal cycles for Grout 4.

Figure 7: 3D image reconstruction of Grout 2 and Grout 4

4.2. Grouts – 28 days of curing period

For 28 days of curing, the Grout 4 shows a compromise in the interface, even though the 7-day cured sample demonstrated a strong bonding in the interface (Figure 8a). The curing process and laboratory temperature are identical to those of the previous samples. As observed from the mechanical tests, Grout 4 showed a minor gradual increase in strength and stiffness for different curing periods. By reconstructing the sample in 3D, the additional volume in the interface is obtained. It shows a uniform slight increase over the entire tube interval.

Figure 8: 3D image reconstruction of Grout 4 and Grout 1, S1

4.3. Clay pellets

A standard consolidation apparatus is utilized to evaluate the swelling capacity of the clay pellets. The experiments are conducted with fresh water and 0.25 mol/L NaCl to observe the effect of salinity on the clay pellets swelling capacity (volume change). The granular clay pellets are placed in the cell after being dried in a 100°C oven for two days. The specimens are then placed within the consolidation cell, subjected to a vertical stress of 1 kPa, while lateral deformation is restricted. As the granular clay pellets saturate, the

volume increases until it reaches a maximum saturation level as observed in Figure 9.

Figure 9: 1D free swell test for freshwater and 0.25 mol/L NaCl

Due to their irregular shape and variable size, the clay pellets are not evenly distributed compared to the grout mixture. Thus, when the upper cap (containing the tube and the thermocouples) is placed, the actual position of the thermocouples differs from the expected. Thus, the spatial monitoring of the temperature is challenging to assess. Clay pellet 1 showed a high swelling capacity and resilience during the thermal cycles without any obvious deformation in the interface area, as shown in Figure 10.

Figure 10: Image reconstruction of Clay pellet 1

Figure 11 shows the disassembled apparatus, with the main cylinder containing the Clay pellet 2, sand layers, and the tube at the centre. The image processing reveals resilience in the thermal cycles with the magnetite particles in place (Figure 12).

Figure 11: Disassembled apparatus prior to micro-CT containing Clay pellet 2

Figure 12: Image reconstruction of Clay pellet 2

5. CONCLUSIONS

An experimental framework was designed and implemented to evaluate the long-term sealing capacity of grout and clay pellet materials under heating and cooling cycles for low-pressure conditions. The experimental demonstration combined with extensive image processing reveals and supports the evidence of the plastic deformation across the interface. In addition, the results are summarized in the following highlights:

- Low stiffness grout corresponds to high plastic deformation.
- Image processing provides an insightful analysis of the increase in the interface area as a function of tube length for 7- and 28-day cured samples.
- Higher concentrations of cementation additives ensure greater strength and stiffness.

- The uniformity across the interface is substantial evidence of thermal expansion.
- For freshwater heating and cooling cycles, the clay pellets show a strong bonding.
- Clay pellet materials show a decrease in vertical strain for 0.25 mol/L NaCl.

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Acknowledgements

This work was funded by the European Union under the Horizon Europe programme (grant no. 1011096566). Views and opinions expressed are, however, those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or CINEA. Neither the European Union nor CINEA can be held responsible for them.